

MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND MODELING OF HIERARCHICALLY-STRUCTURED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Keywords: *Composite Materials, Sandwich Structures, Palmetto Wood, Impact Resistance, Damage Modeling*

1 General Introduction

There is great interest in engineering composite materials at multiple length scales (i.e., hierarchically-structured). Recently, we have investigated the use of nanoscale and microscale carbon fibers in epoxy, thermoplastic, and polymer foam matrices to form hierarchically-structured composite materials. The effects of processing conditions on the dispersion of nanofibers and the subsequent mechanical properties have been characterized through a new multi-scale mechanical characterization approach and model. Motivated by the use of Palmetto wood in protective structures in the Civil and Revolutionary war, it has been used as a bio-inspiration to developed engineering materials with enhanced mechanical properties. The mechanical behavior of Palmetto wood has been characterized by Digital Image Correlation (DIC) [3] under quasi-static bending and low velocity impact (around 30 m/s) at multiple length scales to elucidate the failure mechanism and the role of hierarchical structure in its mechanical behavior. Deformation behavior was quantified by capturing the images of Palmetto wood under three point bend load at several magnifications to capture the macroscale behavior and microscale deformation. Shear dominated debonding by accumulation of shear strain at the macrofiber and porous cellulose interface and pore collapse has been identified as the leading failure mechanisms in Palmetto wood. The damage evolution was investigated and a model based on elastic-plastic behavior has been developed to identify the role of macrofiber concentration and

strain rate in the damage accumulation. Two leading failure mechanisms, namely shear-dominated debonding and pore collapse, have been identified in Palmetto wood. The pore collapse mechanism leads to a plastic strain that accumulates before damage occurs. The present model is developed to take into account both the evolution of damage and plastic strain. Hierarchical structures formed from them have been used to enhance the mechanical behavior of composite materials, such as laminated composites. A model sandwich structure has been fabricated to replicate the Palmetto wood to achieve enhanced mechanical behavior. The sandwich with bio-inspired core has been fabricated by carbon-epoxy composite facesheet and closed-cell soft foam as core. To mimic the structure of the Palmetto wood, carbon rods have been used as reinforcement in the foam core to enhance its mechanical behavior with the nano-enhancement in the epoxy based adhesive used in the interfaces. The damage evolution characteristic of sandwich structure with bio-inspired core has been determined.

2 Research Approach

2.1 Biological Templates

A biological template for creating hierarchically-structured composite materials, Palmetto wood, has been investigated to create porous composites with fiber reinforcement for various applications, such as sandwich structures. Palmetto wood has historically been a very unique structural material for resisting impact due to its evolution to resist hurricanes that

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frequent the state of South Carolina in the United States. A multi-scale mechanical characterization approach has also been used for determining the relationship between the hierarchical structure and mechanical properties of Palmetto wood [1]. Using Digital Image Correlation (DIC) at multiple length scales, it has been possible to identify multiple failure mechanisms associated with the hierarchical structure of Palmetto wood that result in an inelastic response that conforms to Weibull failure statistics [2] as demonstrated by the *Figure 1*. As shown in the *Figure 1*, the macroscale behavior of the Palmetto wood is affected by the strain rate as well as the macrofiber volume fraction. Full field deformation by DIC elucidated the aforementioned failure mechanisms, namely, shear dominated debonding and pore collapse as shown in *Figure 2*. The evolution of macroscale failure with the deformation characteristics in microscale has been correlated and the energy absorbing mechanism has been elucidated. Under the dynamic load, local indentation was identified and the local indentation and global flexural bending have been partitioned to determine the flexural response. The effects of macrofiber volume fraction have been studied with the specimens prepared from several locations of the Palmetto stem. The indentation energy absorption has been found to increase with the increase in macrofiber volume fraction.

Figure 1. Flexural response of Palmetto wood under quasi-static and dynamic load and with 12% and 20% macrofiber volume fraction [4]

Figure 2. (a) Shear strain concentration at the macrofiber-cellulose interface and (b) pore collapse under compression at the micron length scale [2]

A subsequent damage model based on partitioning the elastic and inelastic deformation has been developed to determine the partitioning of this inelastic response between the elastic modulus reductions due to fiber debonding and shear cracking of the porous matrix and the shear localization due to plastic deformation from pore collapse. The change in the partitioning of damage mechanisms due to increased loading rates associated with impact has also been characterized.

2.2 Bio-inspired Sandwich Structures

Sandwich structures with bio-inspired cores using Palmetto Wood as a template have subsequently been created to further investigate the effects of the fiber reinforcement on the partitioning of these failure mechanisms in order to characterize the effects of fiber reinforcement on porous materials for enhancing the energy-absorbing capability and durability of sandwich structures (Figure 3). Carbon epoxy composite has been used as the facesheet and a closed cell soft foam known as Rohacell has been used as core material of this model sandwich structure. Bio-inspired cores were fabricated by using carbon rods (CMF) of a diameter of 0.027” into the foam core. The carbon rods are dipped into epoxy polymer as well as nano-enhanced epoxy polymer to achieve better adhesion with the foam core. Hierarchical structure was achieved by using nano-enhancement in the polymer in terms of Carbon nanofiber (CNF). The amount of carbon rod reinforcement in the foam core was varied. A representative sandwich structure with bio-inspired core is shown in Figure 3. These structures have exhibited transitions in their global stress-strain response that have increases in strength, stiffness, and energy absorbing capability greater than 150% when adding 15-20 vol. % fiber reinforcement transverse to the loading direction. Dynamic full-field deformation measurements have been obtained used Digital Image Correlation (DIC) in order to qualitatively and quantitatively characterize the changes in impact loading response due to the bio-inspired cores.

Figure 3. Sandwich structure with bio-inspired core and dynamic DIC characterization of impact response

2.3 Damage Modeling

The damage evolution of the Palmetto wood has been characterized under quasi-static and dynamic load in three-point bend configuration. We have developed a damage model to characterize the evolution of damage with total strain. Damage is characterized using the parameter, D , related to the current elastic modulus, $E = \sigma/\epsilon_e$, and the original modulus, E_o [5]. This model utilizes the elastic strain associated with the change in elastic modulus due to damage and a partition of total strain between the elastic associated with damage and plastic, ϵ_p , that evolves due to nucleation of pore collapse in the Avrami equation as follows:

$$\epsilon_t = \epsilon_p + \frac{\sigma}{E_o(1-D)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_p = \epsilon_t \left[1 - \exp\left(-a(\epsilon - \epsilon_y)^p\right) \right] \quad (2)$$

By partitioning the elastic and inelastic strain, it is possible to capture the evolution of plastic strain relative to damage evolution. The resulting evolution of the damage parameter (D) and the plastic flexural strain with total strain can be seen for static and dynamic loading for the Palmetto wood in *Figure 4*.

Figure 4: Evolution of (a) damage parameter and (b) plastic flexural strain with total strain for Palmetto wood under quasi-static and dynamic load [4]

The qualitative nature of damage evolution under quasi-static and dynamic load remains same, however, under dynamic load, the damage accumulation occurs at lesser total strain. However, the relation of plastic strain and damage parameter (D) remains similar for both the loading rates and macro-fiber concentration as depicted in *Figure 5*. Thus, it appears that the primary effect of the fiber reinforcement is to increase the stiffness of the core with increasing loading rate and volume fraction of reinforcement, which decreases the macroscopic

strain at which plastic strain and damage accumulate. However, the level of decrease is small enough that the overall effect is to increase the strength of the composite. Thus, the resulting biological composite material has greater energy absorption capability.

Figure 5: Evolution of plastic flexural strain with damage parameter under quasi-static and impact load [4]

The damage evolution in a sandwich structure with the bio-inspired core developed using Palmetto wood as a template is depicted in *Figure 6*. The damage evolution is characterized under quasi-static and dynamic load in three-point-bend configuration. From these results, it can be seen that the use of bio-inspired cores provides a behavior of the sandwich composite that has a dependency between plastic strain and damage evolution that is similar to that of Palmetto wood. However, the exact relationship between these mechanisms does appear to differ due to the differences in the inherent behavior of the synthetic constituents of the bio-inspired core versus the biological constituents in Palmetto wood. Thus, it appears that by combining fiber reinforcement with porous materials, it is possible to create a hierarchically-structured composite sandwich structure where the relationship between plastic strain and damage can be controlled to increase stiffness, strength, and as a result the impact resistance and energy absorbing capability of composite sandwich structures.

Figure 6: Quasi-static and impact stress-strain response (top) and evolution of damage parameter with total strain (bottom) for sandwich structure with bioinspired core

3 Conclusions

A model of damage and plastic strain evolution in fiber-reinforced porous composite structures has been developed for describing their stress-strain response in three-point bending. The foundation of this model is based on the mechanics of failure in the biological composite material known as Palmetto wood. It has been determined that failure occurs by pore collapse in the porous matrix followed by shear-dominated debonding of the fiber-reinforcement. A relationship between the evolution of plastic strain and damage has been identified using this model. It has been determined that this relationship is only slightly affected by the loading rate and volume fraction of fiber reinforcement. The dominant effect appears to be the increase in

stiffness with loading rate and volume fraction of fiber reinforcement, which leads to an increase in strength despite a decrease in the initiation of plastic strain and damage relative to the macroscopic strain. A bio-inspired core has been developed using Palmetto wood as a template, and similar relationships between the evolution of plastic strain and damage have been observed. Thus, it is possible to develop hierarchically-structured polymer composites by combining fiber reinforcement with porous materials in composite sandwich structures that have greater stiffness, strength, and as a result impact resistance and energy absorbing capability.

References

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